

Title:
Entertainment Robots

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- **INTRODUCTION:**

Creative thinking requires imagination, creativity, play, sharing and reflection. This paper presents an architecture for a curious, reconfigurable robot that encourages creative design thinking by permitting designed structures to learn behaviours. These behaviours encourage designers to play with different structures, reflect on the relationship between structure and behavior and imagine new structures. A demonstration of the architecture is described using the Lego Mind storms platform. The demonstration shows how a curious robot can adapt new behaviours in response to changes in its structure, and how this can encourage the creative thinking spiral and creative design.

- **AIM:**

Design can be described as a process of purposeful, constrained decision making requiring exploration and learning. The role of creativity in design has many interpretations, including the distinction between the design of creative artefacts and the evaluation of the processes involved in design as creative. Renick writes that there has been a transition from the Industrial Society to the Information Society and, most recently, the Creative Society. He identifies the need to teach people to use creative thinking processes involving imagination, creativity, play, sharing and reflection.

- **MATERIALS AND METHODS:.**

Plastic, Wood, Metal, Composites,

Classification of Robot:

Robot are categorized depending upon the circuits of the robots and the variety of application it can perform. The robots are classified into three types.

- Simple level robots.
- Middle level robots.
- Complex level robots.

1. **Simple Level Robot:** These are automatic machines which do not contain complex circuit. They are developed just to extend human potential.
For Example: Washing Machine.

2. **Middle Level Robot:** These robot are programmed but can never be programmed. These robot contain sensor based circuit & can perform multiple tasks.
For Example: Full Automatic Washing Machine.

3. **Complex Level Robot:** These robots are programmed and can be reprogrammed as well. They contain complex model based circuit.
For Example: Laptop and Computer.

- **RESULTS:**

Device Layer

Lego Mindstorms robots can be designed with a range of different sensors and actuators including sensors for colour, light, sound or distance to objects and actuators for servo motors. NXT sensors and actuators are heterogeneous and return different numbers and types of outputs. The device layer constructs a standardised, context-free grammar (CFG) [5] representation of sensor data and available actions and communicates this to the agent layer.

Device Manager: The device manager identifies the sensor devices S1, S2, S3 ... attached to the robot. Data from all sensors is encapsulated as a single sensation **S** represented as a variable length string of label-value pairs. The device manager also identifies the actuators A1, A2, A3 ... attached to the robot.

Resource Manager: The resource manager communicates sensations and actions between the agent and the devices via Bluetooth. In the demonstration in Section 3, the Agent layer is run on a PC separate from the NXT brick. The Lejos Java firmware does not currently offer sufficient support for the complex programming constructs required to implement a curious agent. In future it is envisaged that it will be possible to run the Agent layer on the NXT brick and the resource manager will no longer be required.

- **CONCLUSIONS:**

This paper has presented an architecture for curious, reconfigurable robots for creative play. Curious robots can learn new behavior in response to changes in their structure. The robots in this paper use a computational model of curiosity to identify new goals and reinforcement learning to develop new behavior in response to those Goals. An initial demonstration of curious robots using the Lego Mind storms platform shows how curious, reconfigurable robots can influence the creative thinking spiral. The adaptive behavior of the robot in response to its changing structure encourages reflection, imagination and ongoing creative play. In future, this research may proceed in two directions. First, user studies can provide insight into the impact of this technology on creative play. In conjunction with this, the technology itself can be further developed with the aim of designing robots that can develop complex, realistic and meaningful behaviours. Such robots might have applications beyond entertainment robots to explorer robots in spaces or assistant robots in the home or industry.

- **KEYWORDS:**

Curiosity, motivated reinforcement learning, robots, creative design, creative play.

- **BIOGRAPHY:**

My Self Chintan Patel from India, I have completed my MBA (Master of Business Administration) With IB (International Business). I have two Years' experience in Robotics Company as a Head of Technical and HR Department. Currently I am a Founder of VNC Robotics and Automation Company and VNC Robotics is an assembler, distributor and service provider for service robots having consumer, industrial, commercial application. Our society lies in providing the best robots for cleaning applications at the most affordable prices.

About My Role in VNC Robotics Company The brains behind the technology, boasting the required technical expertise to successfully execute projects from a variety of industrial and consumer projects has been instrumental in motivating his employees in overcoming challenges. Strategic and knowledgeable approach in the robotics field has set the bar for everyone in the field.